

Stereoselective synthesis of *trans* acetoxy β -lactams under microwave irradiation

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Microwave-induced racemic and asymmetric synthesis of *trans* acetoxy β -lactams is performed following a nucleophilic substitution reaction of *cis* 3-mesyloxy β -lactams with sodium acetate. This method is applicable to obtain a few unusual stereodefined *trans* acetoxy β -lactams.

Keywords: Microwave, β -lactam, stereoselective, inversion of configuration.

Introduction

Stereoselective synthesis of organic molecules is the subject of intensive investigation¹. Synthesis of β -lactams as pure *trans* isomer remains a challenge because most of the available methods produce *cis* stereoisomers². Synthetic studies to solve this problem and to obtain *trans* stereoisomeric β -lactams is advanced and some successes are realized in the field of racemic β -lactams. However, synthesis of *trans* optically active enantiomeric acetoxy β -lactams or any other derivatives remain unexplored. In the early days β -lactam research, scientists mostly concentrate on the synthesis of the *cis* isomer because only this form demonstrates clinical activity³. But, discovery of several clinically active *trans* β -lactams opens the challenge of their synthesis as well⁴. We describe here a simple and fast method for the preparation of racemic and chiral *trans* 3-acetoxy β -lactams through microwave-induced reaction of *cis* 3-mesyloxy β -lactams with sodium acetate⁵.

Results and discussion

Racemic *cis* 3-mesyloxy acetoxy β -lactam **1** were prepared through racemic acetoxy and hydroxyl compounds. Reaction of **1** with sodium acetate in DMSO under microwave

irradiation method produced exclusively *trans* 3-acetoxy β -lactam **2** in good yield (Scheme 1 and Table 1).

Scheme 1. Microwave induced synthesis *trans* monocyclic β -lactam.

Table 1

Entry	1		T ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Time (h)	Yield (%)
	R ¹	R ²			
1	Ph	Ph	50	2	80
2	Ph	PMP	50	2	75
3	Ph	<i>p</i> -Methyl	50	4	70
4	Ph	<i>p</i> -Fluorophenyl	50	5	70

Following an identical route *cis* 3-mesyloxy 3*R*,4*S* (**3**) (derived from D-glycerldehyde acetonide) and *cis* 3-mesyloxy 3*S*,4*R* (**4**) (derived from L-glycerldehyde acetonide) were subjected to react with sodium acetate under microwave condition. The product obtained from this route is *trans* 3-acetoxy

Scheme 2. Microwave induced synthesis *trans* monocyclic chiral β -lactam (+)-enantiomers.

Table 2

Entry	1		T ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Time (h)	Yield (%)
	R ¹	R ²			
1	Ph	Ph	50	2	80
2	Ph	PMP	50	2	75
3	Ph	<i>p</i> -Methyl	50	4	70
4	Ph	Cinnamyl	50	4	75

β -lactams (Scheme 2). The mechanism of this process can be explained by a nucleophilic substitution bimolecular pathway.

The enantiomeric β -lactams **3** have been also isomerized at C-3 position successfully under the discussed conditions (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3. Microwave induced synthesis *trans* monocyclic chiral β -lactam (-)-enantiomers.

Table 3

Entry	1		T ($^\circ\text{C}$)	Time (h)	Yield (%)
	R ¹	R ²			
1	Ph	Ph	50	2	80
2	Ph	PMP	50	2	75

The mesylate group at the C-3 position of the racemic and chiral *cis* 3-mesyl derivatives undergoes reaction with highly polar acetate anion which is also solvated by DMSO.

Moreover, microwave irradiation supplies the necessary energy for the departure of the mesylate group which has an excellent leaving group property. The process results in inversion of configuration at the C-center of the *cis* β -lactams (Scheme 4).

Scheme 4. Plausible mechanism of concomitant demesylation.

Experimental

A representative procedure is given below. In a 125 mL Erlenmeyer Flask, DMSO (2 mL) was added to the β -lactam **1** (1 mmol). To the reaction mixture sodium acetate (3 mmol) were then added and the reaction mixture was irradiated in a domestic microwave oven for 2–5 min at low power level. To the reaction mixture dichloromethane (20 mL) was added and it was shaken. The reaction mixture was washed with brine (2 mL). The organic extracts were then evaporated and passed through a short column of silica gel (5 g) using ethylacetate and hexanes (20:80) as the solvent to afford the pure product **2**.

Conclusions

Stereodefined β -lactams with *trans* 3-acetoxy in racemic and optically active forms are prepared using a domestic microwave. These products are useful because optical isomers as reported herein are not prepared before. Therefore, research directed using these compounds is valuable. It is important to note that the synthesis of *trans* β -lactams with defined stereochemistry is a challenging objective.

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